

Synthesis and characterization of metal complexes of manganese-, cobalt- and zinc(II) with Schiff base and some neutral ligand

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A series of complexes of the types $ML_2L'_2$, where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}$, $L = 2$ -pyridylalldoxime, $L' =$ neutral ligand (quinoline, isoquinoline, pyridine and γ -picoline) and MLL'_2 , where $M = Zn^{II}$, $L = 2$ -pyridylalldoxime and $L' =$ neutral ligand, have been synthesized. The complexes are monomeric and non-electrolytic in nature. The magnetic moment values indicate paramagnetic nature of the complexes of Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and diamagnetic of Zn^{II} . IR spectra reveal the coordination of Schiff base ligand and neutral ligand. The electronic spectral data suggests octahedral geometry for the complexes of Mn^{II} and Co^{II} but tetrahedral for Zn^{II} .

Transition metal complexes using donor ligands are finding extensive uses¹. Here, some complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} with Schiff base ligand 2-pyridylalldoxime and some neutral ligand (quinoline, isoquinoline, pyridine and γ -picoline) are reported.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are insoluble in water but soluble in dioxane and DMF. The analytical data indicate 1 : 2 : 2 metal 2-pyridylalldoxime : neutral ligand stoichiometry for all the Co^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes but 1 : 1 : 2 stoichiometry for the Zn^{II} complexes. Low molar conductance values of two complexes ($60-80 \Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate their non-electrolytic nature however the values ($150-200 \Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) for all the other complexes indicate their electrolytic nature. The complexes are stable up to 250° . The molecular weight (Rast's comphor method) of the complexes indicate their monomeric nature.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd	Colour	Metal % Found/(Calcd)	μ_{eff} B M
$[Mn(PA)_2Cl_2]$	Yellow	15.01 (14.85)	6.1
$[Mn(PA)_2(Qn)_2]Cl_2$	White	9.01 (8.74)	5.9
$[Mn(PA)_2(IQn)_2]Cl_2$	Pink	9.01 (8.74)	5.98
$[Co(PA)_2Cl_2]$	Orange	15.91 (15.76)	4.9
$[Co(PA)_2(Qn)_2]Cl_2$	Yellow	9.68 (9.32)	4.8
$[Co(PA)_2(IQn)_2]Cl_2$	Green	9.68 (9.32)	4.78
$[Co(PA)_2(Py)_2]Cl_2$	Green	11.31 (11.07)	4.65
$[Co(PA)_2(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]Cl_2$	Brown	10.72 (10.51)	4.5
$[Zn(PA)_2Cl_2]$	White	17.46 (17.18)	Dia
$[Zn(PA)_2(Qn)_2]Cl_2$	White	12.76 (12.65)	Dia
$[Zn(PA)_2(IQn)_2]Cl_2$	White	12.82 (12.65)	Dia
$[Zn(PA)_2(Py)_2]Cl_2$	White	15.79 (15.69)	Dia
$[Zn(PA)_2(\gamma\text{-pic})_2]Cl_2$	White	14.81 (14.70)	Dia

All complexes gave satisfactory C, H, N and Cl⁻ analyses, Py = pyridine, Qn = quinoline, IQn = isoquinoline, γ -pic = γ -picoline, PA = 2-pyridylalldoxime

IR spectra of 2-pyridylalldoxime (PA) show a broad and medium band around $3100-3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to CH stretch of aromatic ring. The ligand band at 2900 cm^{-1} (OH) disappears in the metal complexes indicating deprotonation of the phenolic OH group on coordination. The band at 1570 cm^{-1} ($C=N$ of pyridyl N)² is shifted to lower energy by $10-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the involvement of pyridyl-N on coordination. The band at 1580 cm^{-1} due to neutral ligand (quinoline, isoquinoline, pyridine and γ -picoline) suggests coordination through N-atom³. This is corroborated by the presence of a band at 1530 cm^{-1} ($C=C + C-N$).

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes show bands at 9500 and 18000 cm^{-1} assigned to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, respectively, which suggest an octahedral geometry around the metal ion⁴. The magnetic moment values ($4.5-4.9 \text{ B M.}$)⁵ also support the above structure. The electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes show bands at 14000 , 16500 and 19500 cm^{-1} assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}({}^4G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}({}^4G)$, respectively, which suggest octahedral geometry around the metal ion⁶. The magnetic moment value ($5.9-6.1 \text{ B M.}$) also supports the above structure. As expected the Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic. On the basis of elemental analysis, conductance and spectral data tetrahedral geometry is suggested for the Zn^{II} complexes⁷.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A R grade. The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of an aqueous ethanolic solution of metal chlorides (0.05 mol in 40 ml), Schiff base ligand 2-pyridylalldoxime (0.10 mol in 40 ml

ethanol) and the neutral ligands (quinoline, isoquinoline, pyridine and γ -picoline; 0.10 mol in 40 ml ethanol) on a steam-bath for 30 min. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The metals were analysed by standard procedures⁸. C, H, N were analysed using a CE 440 analyser. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu-480-spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 160-A spectrophotometer. Conductance was measured in 10^{-3} M methanol solution with a Systronics-303 conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy balance using diamagnetic correction by Pascal's constant.

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